

Partner Profile

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

A self-developed profile (organisational CV) to present to potential coordinators and consortia when expressing interest in participation.

Benefits

Building and being part of a diverse project consortium is the foundation of a successful MA project proposal. A partner profile is a way to quickly, concisely and effectively inform other partners of your capabilities, capacities, expertise and main interests.

Practical recommendations

Be specific & tailor it!

You will make the best impression if you tailor your profile to the call text your organisation is interested in. You can have a general paragraph to introduce your organisation, but highlight the specific aspects most relevant to the issue in the call text. Why is your organisation so pertinent to take along in a potential project for this call?

Clarify your competences

Your organisation profile should include the key competences of your organisation. As you are expressing your interest for a multi-actor approach call, also include any relevant experiences related to working in multi-actor settings.

First impressions matter

We provide you with a template for a partner profile as a source of inspiration. Don't make it longer than 2 pages and apply your own organisation's visual identity to make it look clean and professional!

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Work with a diversity of backgrounds

Balance the needs of both yourself as the consortium as a whole

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Partner profile example structure available on Zenodo](#)

**right click to open*

PREMIERE
Example of a Partner Profile

1. Identifiers of your organisation/company

Organisation/company name	
Type of organisation	
Organisation size	
Contact person	
E-mail	
Telephone	
Address	
Country	
Website	

2. Organisation profile
Introduce your organisation, its vision, mission, core values and core business. What are you best known for in your specific context?
Describe how you are embedded in your context: how is your organisation connected to other players/stakeholders in the sector? Who does your organisation most often work with?

3. Envisaged role within project and competences
Describe why you are interested in the specific call and what competences you can bring to the Multi-actor project group. Which competences do you bring to the table? What is your experience with working in multi-actor settings?
Include what type of role you are looking for in the project: would you like to be highly involved, also in the management of the project as a Work Package or Task leader or are you more looking for contributing technical expertise in very distinct and well-defined activities? What can you provide?

4. Relevant projects and experience
List most relevant projects or initiatives your organisation is working on/has part in of the scope of the call text.

5. Topics of interest for Horizon Europe
If there would be any other topics of interest in the current call your organisation is interested in, you could list them here.

Figure: Profile template

Credit: Woning, J. (2025, juni 24). Partner Profile example. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15728790>